

THE INFLUENCE OF FOOD LABELING AND BRAND NAME OF FOOD PRODUCTS ON CONSUMERS FOOD CHOICES IN YENAGOA LOCAL GOVERNMENT AREA OF BAYELSA STATE

¹Donald-Ase, Mary, ²Akhigbe, Evelyn Omolegho, ³Nwosu, Emmanuel C., ⁴Ifeanyi-Omeh, Chioma L., ⁵Gbenga-Philips, Peace C., ⁶Allison, Trust-Jah Tuae gwuchukwu and ⁷Kio-Mikietuoniso, Ogechi Attracta

^{1,3 and 7} Department of Human Nutrition and Dietetics, Faculty of Health Sciences, Bayelsa Medical University, Yenegoa, Bayelsa State, Nigeria.

²Nutrition and Dietetics Department, Niger Delta University Teaching Hospital, Okolobiri, Bayelsa State, Nigeria; Multidisciplinary Unit, West African Society of Parenteral and Enteral Nutrition, Abuja FCT, Nigeria.

^{4,5}Nutrition and Dietetics Department, Federal Medical Center, Yenagoa, Bayelsa State, Nigeria.

⁶Multidisciplinary Unit, West African Society of Parenteral and Enteral Nutrition, Abuja FCT; Research Wing, Distributions.Nigeria Limited, Umuahia, Abia State; Department of Psychology, Faculty of Social Sciences, Imo State University, Owerri, Imo State, Nigeria.

Corresponding Email: allison@waspen.org

Phone Number+2348166282392

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17855460>

Keywords: Influence, Food Labeling, Brand Name, Food Products, Consumers.	Abstract: Objectives: This study was designed to determine the influence of food labels and brand names of food products on consumers' food choices, and to assess the consumers' knowledge and perception on food labels and brand name of food products in Yenagoa Local Government area of Bayelsa State. Methodology: A total of 200 respondents were selected for the study using the convenience sampling technique to collect data from commercial supermarkets in Yenagoa LGA of Bayelsa State, this technique supported in finding relevant respondents who willingly participated in the study and a structured questionnaire was used to illicit information on the Socio demographic/economic characteristics, Consumers perception on Nutrition information on food labels and Consumers
---	--

Donald-Ase, Mary, Akhigbe, Evelyn Omolegho, Nwosu, Emmanuel C., Ifeanyi-Omeh, Chioma L., Gbenga-Philips, Peace C., Allison, Trust-Jah Tuae gwuchukwu and Kio-Mikietuoniso, Ogechi Attracta

perception on the purchase of Branded food products. A total of 200 questionnaires were distributed, filled and collected and 62 commercial supermarkets in nine major wards of the LGA were selected which includes both urban and semi urban communities. Also consumers who use packaged foods were considered and interviewed in the 62 supermarkets.

Results: *Results revealed that 67(33.5%) were male and 133(66.5%) were female, 27(13.5%) had informal education, 11(5.5%) had primary education while 29(14.5%) had secondary education. 49(24.5%) are self-employed, while 76(38.0%) are civil servants, 3(1.5%) earn ₦30, 000 monthly, while 109(54.5%) earn more than ₦90, 000 monthly. Data entry and processing were done using the descriptive statistical analysis on frequency tables and percentages. Descriptive and inferential statistics was used to analyze the variable with significance difference at $P < 0.05$.*

Conclusion: *Food labels and brand name of food products allows the consumers have the knowledge and guidance towards the food products they purchase; it is also a legal requirement to give an idea of the quality of the food product. In the study most of the consumers do not mind reading food labels, and do not trust the write up on the food manufacturers. It is also observed in the study that buying well branded food products is a symbol of prestige, health and wellness of my family. Nutritional information on Food labels and brand names of food products also influenced the choices of food products purchased by consumers.*

Introduction

Food labels are information written on food products, it is one of the most important and direct means of communicating the food product information to consumers. Internationally, the accepted definition of a food label is “any mark, brand, or tag, any pictorial or descriptive information, written or printed, stenciled, marked, embossed or impressed or attached to a container of food or food product”,

(Prinsloo, Van der Merwe, Bosman, & Erasmus, 2012). This information must include items such as ingredients, quality of product and nutritional value of the product and can accompany the food or be displayed on the food product to promote its sale. A food label is the identification of the nutritional information and facts of the food product about what is present inside the pack. Food labels notify consumers about the nutritional values and ingredients,

Donald-Ase, Mary, Akhigbe, Evelyn Omolegho, Nwosu, Emmanuel C., Ifeanyi-Omeh, Chioma L., Gbenga-Philips, Peace C., Allison, Trust-Jah Tuae gwuchukwu and Kio-Mikietuoniso, Ogechi Attracta

manufacturer's health claims, possible allergens or some other potentially threatening health information. All these information enables the consumer decide whether to consume the product or not (Verbeke & Ward, 2006).

Food labels also contain information about the shelf life, storage conditions, instructions for use, manufacturers list of ingredients, additives and allergens of the food product (Food Safety and Standards, 2011). According to Codex Alimentarius Commission, Nutrition label is defined as “a description intended to inform the consumer of the nutritional properties of the food as written on the food label or package in the form of a table and includes Nutrient Declaration, Serving Size and % Daily Value”, (The Codex Alimentarius Commission Food Labeling, 2007). It is essential to read and understand both the food and nutrition labels in order to make healthier food choices, (Vojir, Schubl & Elmadfa, 2012).

According to Food Safety and Standards (Labeling and Display) Regulations, (2020), the conditions for labeling food products should include the following:

- Presence of Labeling information on all packaged food
- Information described or presented on any food labeling should be true and reliable

- Information described or presented on any food labeling should not be misleading or deceptive
- Food label should not be described or presented in any labeling ways that is going to make a wrong impression to consumers
- Food labels should be applied in a way that they won't become separated from the container or the packaging material
- All printing or embossing on the food label should be clear, conspicuous, permanent and be readable by the consumer
- Nutrition labels must display the amount of energy (calories and kilojoules), carbohydrates, sugars, proteins and salt (expressed in grams) and the amount of fat, eg, saturated fat, all presented per 100g or per 100 ml of the food.

Most of the time, limited time and resources often make the process of purchase of food products done in a hurry and consumers miss paying attention to what is written on food packaging. Nutrition labels, ingredient labels, and even product packaging can reveal to consumers about what is to be purchased and consume.

Purpose of Labeling Food Products, according to McGuire S. Institute of Medicine, (2012),

Donald-Ase, Mary, Akhigbe, Evelyn Omolegho, Nwosu, Emmanuel C., Ifeanyi-Omeh, Chioma L., Gbenga-Philips, Peace C., Allison, Trust-Jah Tuae gwuchukwu and Kio-Mikietuoniso, Ogechi Attracta

Food labeling intends to protect the health and well-being of consumers. It helps consumers learn about:

- The amount of ingredients present in the food products
- Percentage of each ingredient in the food products
- The quantity of food nutrients present in the food, presented either in weight or as percentage.
- The ingredients that can induce allergies

Benefits of food labels

Food labels are legal requirements to guide consumers towards the food products they purchase; it allows consumers acquire knowledge about the food product. It can help consumers that are on specific diets to maintain their diets. Food labels also give an idea of the quality of food product. Most food packaging labels contain a separate list of ingredients used to manufacture the product, including preservatives.

Food quality – Food labels help to provide warnings and important information like the storage conditions, and cooking instructions, to keep food safe from microbial contamination and spoilage.

Health – Food Labels highlight food composition which also includes the food nutrients, calories, fats, etc, this helps the

consumer monitor their nutrient intake, to help prevent some certain illnesses.

Specific ingredients – Food labels inform consumers about special dietary requirements and whether or not they contain ingredients that they should avoid, considering their health.

Food wastage – Food labels can prevent food wastage, by informing the consumer on the expiry dates and product shelf life, this is important to prevent sickness from eating expired food products or wasting the food

Food Labels must also include the following, according to Temple, (2020)

The name of food: This must be a true representation of the food product and should not be false or misleading to the consumer

The list of ingredients: The list of ingredients used to make the product should be written in a descending order of weight

The percentage of certain ingredients: This should be stated and the quantity of the ingredient in percentages in the ingredient list.

Cooking instructions if necessary: This should include the cooking temperature and cooking time

It should also include ‘best before’ and the dates reflected on the label: By putting these dates on the food products will help consumers store and use food safely, as well as reduce food waste.

Storage instructions: To enable the consumers safely store products before and after opening

Donald-Ase, Mary, Akhigbe, Evelyn Omolegho, Nwosu, Emmanuel C., Ifeanyi-Omeh, Chioma L., Gbenga-Philips, Peace C., Allison, Trust-Jah Tuaegwuchukwu and Kio-Mikietuoniso, Ogechi Attracta

the packaging, which will ensure they remain safe for consumption, instructions should include, eg ‘Store in a cool, dry place. Once opened, refrigerate and consume within a number of days.’

Contact details: Include the name of the business and a contact address.

It is of note that healthy food information are increasingly appearing on food packaging, for example ‘reduced in salt’ and ‘reduced fat’. This can convey important health information to reduce consumers’ flavor expectations of food and inhibit their buying needs (Ye, Morrin, and Kampfer, 2019).

Brand Name of food Products

The brand name of a product is the name given to the product by the manufacturer and under which the product is sold, it is the name by which a certain brand or make of commodity is known, which is used to identify the family of that product (Ushiana, Vingerhoeds, Kanemura, Kaneko & De Wijk, 2021). A brand name is sometimes simply the name that the producer gave to the product, the signature that gives credit to the manufacturer of the particular product that sets it apart from those created by others. It is for Identification, to differentiate it from other likes or similar brands. It is also for verification, to authenticate that a product is the genuine or desired article, (Shirazi, Lorestani, & Mazidi, 2013).

Effects of Brand Name on Consumers Food Choice

Brand name plays a crucial role to enhance and positively change people's buying behavior. It influences food perceptions (Finkelstein & Fishbach, 2010). On the other hand, labeling and packaging have a significant impact on consumer choices and preferences (Kozup, Creyer, and Burton, 2003).

- Consumers want trust, comfort and satisfaction in the food products they buy, especially if the brands they are used to have been offering to them positive experiences
- Consumers believes that a particular food brand name is trustworthy, which gives them peace of mind when buying it.
- They buy brand name of food products which have offered them good experiences in the past
- They would want to portray a certain image, if many shoppers are extremely loyal to their beloved brands, especially the brand name that is in vogue.
- Some also buy food products for the first time with the hope that it provides quality experience, quality taste or nutritional value.
- Popular brand names typically have shown a consistency in product quality that has contributed to the promotion of the brand, hence consumers go for them.

Donald-Ase, Mary, Akhigbe, Evelyn Omolegho, Nwosu, Emmanuel C., Ifeanyi-Omeh, Chioma L., Gbenga-Philips, Peace C., Allison, Trust-Jah Tuaegwuchukwu and Kio-Mikietuoniso, Ogechi Attracta

- Most times, consumers rely on prior experiences or public comments when selecting brands.
- Consumers have the desire to fit in, in social circle for this reason they buy brand names because they believe the brands will contribute to greater social acceptance.
- Consumers often buy popular brands that are perceived as high class.

The brand name is tied to the general information about the product and can convey valuable health messages similar to food health labels. Brand names on food packaging have effects on consumer preferences. It also inspire healthy food marketing. Consumers feel that there may be little difference in the quality of food products from their preferred brands, (Hansen, 2002). Though, it is also thought that specific brands vary widely based on the brand itself.

There are some factors that also affect the behaviour of consumers when choosing brand of products, for example ethnicity, culture & social group preferences, as well as food availability and household technology. There are also differences among individuals in age, sex, education, standard of living, physiological and psychological make-up, (Liao, Corsi, Chrysochou & Lockshin 2015).

Some of the factors that influence consumers to choose brand names include the following:

Psychological Factors - When a consumer is well motivated, it influences their buying behavior especially, when a customer sees advertisements, promotions, customer reviews and social media, about a particular product, they develop an impression about the product.

The attitudes and beliefs - Consumers have certain attitudes and beliefs that influence their buying decisions, this attitude play a significant role in defining the brand image in their mind.

Social Factors – people social lives are influenced by the people that live around them, they try to imitate others and also wish to be socially accepted in the society, this influence their food choices.

Family - Family plays a significant role in influencing brand names of food products, the influence most of the time is developed from childhood by watching family continuously buy particular products and even when they grow up

Cultural factors – The set of values and ideologies that people belong to, in a particular community is highly influenced by the culture relating to that community. Culture have strong influence on consumer buying behavior which include the needs, the wants, preferences, basic values, perceptions and behaviors that are observed and learned from their family

Donald-Ase, Mary, Akhigbe, Evelyn Omolegho, Nwosu, Emmanuel C., Ifeanyi-Omeh, Chioma L., Gbenga-Philips, Peace C., Allison, Trust-Jah Tuaegwuchukwu and Kio-Mikietuoniso, Ogechi Attracta

members and other important people around them.

Social Class – Not just the social class that determines the factors influencing food brand names, other factors such as occupation, family background, education and residence location, the income, also influence the consumer buying behavior.

Personal Factors - Personal factors differ from person to person, thereby influencing different perceptions and consumer buying behaviors, and these include, age, the buying choices of youth differ from that of middle-aged people and the elderly people.

Income - Income has the ability and power to influence the buying behavior of people, the higher the income, the higher the purchasing

power of consumers, and vice-versa. When a consumer has higher income, it gives them more opportunity to spend on luxurious food products. Whereas low and middle-income group consumers spend less

Occupation - For example, it is noted that health professionals know the benefits of good food, hence would go for it than other professionals

Lifestyle - The buying behavior of consumers are highly influenced by their lifestyle, a consumer that leads a healthy lifestyle, will avoid junk foods

Savings - If a consumer decided to save more, then their expenditure on buying also reduces and if a consumer is not interested in saving, it also affect their buying power.

Results

Table 1: Socio demographic/economic characteristics of the respondents

Variables	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Age		
15 – 20	9	4.5
21 – 30	15	7.5
31 – 40	56	28
41 – 50	63	31
51 – 60	57	23.5
Total	200	100
Gender		
Male	67	33.5
Female	133	66.5

Donald-Ase, Mary, Akhigbe, Evelyn Omolegho, Nwosu, Emmanuel C., Ifeanyi-Omeh, Chioma L., Gbenga-Philips, Peace C., Allison, Trust-Jah Tuae gwuchukwu and Kio-Mikietuoniso, Ogechi Attracta

Multidisciplinary Journal of Current Research and Review

Multi. J. Curr. Res. Rev.

Volume: 8; Issue: 06,

November-December, 2025

ISSN: 2763 –3642

Impact Factor: 6.41

Advance Scholars Publication

Published by International Institute of Advance Scholars Development

<https://aspjournals.net/Journals/index.php/mjerr/index>

Total	200	100
Religion		
Christianity	173	86.5
Islam	19	9.5
Traditional	8	4.0
Others	-	-
Total	200	100

Marital Status

Married	129	64.5
Single	40	20.0
Widowed/Widower	20	10.0
Separated/Divorced	11	5.5
Total	200	100

Educational Attainment

Informal	27	13.5
Primary	11	5.5
Secondary	29	14.5
Tertiary	133	66.5
Total	200	100

Variables	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Occupation		
Business	67	33.5
Self Employed	49	24.5
Civil Servant	76	38.0
Others Specially	8	4.0
Total	200	100
Monthly income		
Below 30,000	3	1.50

Donald-Ase, Mary, Akhigbe, Evelyn Omolegho, Nwosu, Emmanuel C., Ifeanyi-Omeh, Chioma L., Gbenga-Philips, Peace C., Allison, Trust-Jah Tuaegwuchukwu and Kio-Mikietuoniso, Ogechi Attracta

Multidisciplinary Journal of Current Research and Review

Multi. J. Curr. Res. Rev.

Volume: 8; Issue: 06,

November-December, 2025

ISSN: 2763 –3642

Impact Factor: 6.41

Advance Scholars Publication

Published by International Institute of Advance Scholars Development

<https://aspjournals.net/Journals/index.php/mjerr/index>

31,000 – 60,000	34	17.0
61,000 – 90,000	109	54.5
90,000 and above	54	27.0
Total	200	100

Family Size

<3	41	20.5
4 – 6	126	63.0
7 – 9	21	10.5
10<	12	1.0
Total	200	100

Ethnicity

Igbo	47	23.5
Yoruba	19	9.5
Hausa	12	6.0
Ijaw	71	33.5
Others	51	25.5
Total	200	100

Place of Residence

Rural	17	8.5
Urban	183	91.5
Total	200	100

How much do you spend on monthly feeding

30,000	4	2.0
30,000 – 60,000	31	15.5
61,000 – 90,000	77	38.5
<90,000	88	44.0
Total	200	100

Donald-Ase, Mary, Akhigbe, Evelyn Omolegho, Nwosu, Emmanuel C., Ifeanyi-Omeh, Chioma L., Gbenga-Philips, Peace C., Allison, Trust-Jah Tuaegwuchukwu and Kio-Mikietuoniso, Ogechi Attracta

Table 2: Consumers perception on Nutrition information on food labels

Table 3: Consumers perception on purchase of Brand names of food products

Factors	True (%)	False (%)	Total (%)
Rich people generally buy branded food products	66 (33.0)	134 (67.0)	200 (100)
I don't mind food products labels before purchasing my food products	127 (63.5)	73 (36.5)	200 (100)
Buying well branded food products is a symbol of prestige	164 (82)	36 (18)	200 (100)
I don't trust the manufacture's write up on the food labels, I	63 (31.5)	137 (68.5)	200 (100)
I buy branded food products because I am concerned about the health and wellness of my family	188 (94)	12 (6)	200 (100)
To avoid reading food labels	41 (20.5)	159 (79.5)	200 (100)
I have found that my family and friends always buy branded food products	66 (33)	134 (67)	200 (100)
It is good to read label information for the right food choices	47 (23.5)	153 (76.5)	200 (100)
I am always interested in brand names of food products before purchase	167 (83.5)	33 (16.5)	200 (100)
The details given on food label guide me at the time of shopping	183 (91.5)	17 (8.5)	200 (100)
I don't mind food brand names before purchasing my food products	29 (14.5)	171 (85.5)	200 (100)
It is not easy to read and understand healthy package food information without professional advice	170 (85.0)	30 (15.0)	200 (100)
I don't have the knowledge of any good food brand names so I purchase anyone that is available	60 (30)	140 (70)	200 (100)
Food labels help you compare similar products to make healthier food choices	66 (33.0)	134 (67.0)	200 (100)
It is good to follow the food brand names that has the highest advertisement	38 (19.0)	162	200 (100)
I find it difficult to search relevant information for the selection of healthy packaged foods	161 (80.5)	39 (19.5)	200 (100)
I find it difficult to know the best food products through the brand names	47 (23.5)	153 (76.5)	200 (100)
A familiar brand name is better than new brands	183 (91.5)	17 (8.5)	200 (100)

Discussion

The study investigated the influence of food labeling and brand name of food products on consumers' food choices in Yenagoa Local Government Area of Bayelsa State, Nigeria. The results showed that food labeling and brand

name have a significant impact on consumers' food choices. The majority of the respondents (91.5%) reported that labeling guide them during their shopping time, and 83.5% indicated that the brand name influences their purchasing decision.

Donald-Ase, Mary, Akhigbe, Evelyn Omolegho, Nwosu, Emmanuel C., Ifeanyi-Omeh, Chioma L., Gbenga-Philips, Peace C., Allison, Trust-Jah Tuaegwuchukwu and Kio-Mikietuoniso, Ogechi Attracta

Multidisciplinary Journal of Current Research and Review

Multi. J. Curr. Res. Rev.

Volume: 8; Issue: 06,

November-December, 2025

ISSN: 2763 –3642

Impact Factor: 6.41

Advance Scholars Publication

Published by International Institute of Advance Scholars Development

<https://aspjournals.net/Journals/index.php/mjerr/index>

The findings of this study are consistent with previous research, which suggests that food labeling and brand name are important factors in consumers' food choices (Kumar & Kapoor, 2017). The study also revealed that consumers are becoming increasingly health-conscious and are seeking more information about the food products they consume. This is reflected in the growing demand for clear and accurate food labeling.

The study also found that brand name has significant influence on consumers' food choices, with many respondents indicating that they prefer to purchase products from well-known and reputable brands. This is because consumers associate well-known brands with high-quality products and are willing to pay a premium for them.

Conclusion

The study highlights the importance of food labeling and brand name in influencing

References

Finkelstein S.R. and Fishbach A. (2010). When Healthy Food Makes You Hungry. **J. Consum. Res.** 37, 357– 367.

Food Safety and Standards (Food Products Standards and Food Additives) Regulations (2011). Food Safety and Standards Authority of India. Product Standards. Food Safety and Standards

consumers' food choices in Yenagoa Local Government Area of Bayelsa State, Nigeria. Food manufacturers and marketers should take cognizance of these factors when developing and promoting their products. Clear and accurate labeling, combined with effective branding strategies, can help to increase consumer trust and loyalty, ultimately driving sales and revenue growth.

Recommendation

1. Food manufacturers should ensure that their products have clear and accurate labeling, including information on ingredients, nutritional content, and expiration dates.
2. Marketers should develop effective branding strategies that communicate the quality and value of their products to consumers.
3. Regulatory agencies should enforce strict guidelines on food labeling and branding to protect consumers from misleading or deceptive practices.

(Labelling and Display) Regulations, 2020.

Hansen T. (2002). The effect of physical surroundings in usage situations on consumer perception of food quality and on consumer emotions. *Journal of International Consumer Marketing*, 15(1), 31–51.

Donald-Ase, Mary, Akhigbe, Evelyn Omolegho, Nwosu, Emmanuel C., Ifeanyi-Omeh, Chioma L., Gbenga-Philips, Peace C., Allison, Trust-Jah Tuae gwuchukwu and Kio-Mikietuoniso, Ogechi Attracta

Multidisciplinary Journal of Current Research and Review

Multi. J. Curr. Res. Rev.

Volume: 8; Issue: 06,

November-December, 2025

ISSN: 2763 –3642

Impact Factor: 6.41

Advance Scholars Publication

Published by International Institute of Advance Scholars Development

<https://aspjournals.net/Journals/index.php/mjerr/index>

- Kozup J.C., Creyer E.H. and Burton S. (2003). Making Healthful Food Choices: The Influence of Health Claims and Nutrition Information on Consumers' Evaluations of Packaged Food Products and Restaurant Menu Items. *Journal of Marketing*, 67, 19–34.
- Kumar, P., & Kapoor, S. (2017). Impact of food labeling on consumer behaviour. *Journal of Food Science and Technology*, 54(13), 4231-4241.
- Liao L.X., Corsi A.M., Chrysochou P. and Lockshin L. (2015). Emotional responses towards Food packaging: A joint application of self-report and physiological measures of emotion. *Food Qual. Prefer.* 42:48–55.
- McGuire S. (2012). Institute of Medicine. *Front-of-Package Nutrition Rating Systems & Symbols: Promoting Healthier Choices*. Washington, DC: The National Academies Press. *Advances in Nutrition*. 3(3):332-3.
- Prinsloo N., Van der Merwe D., Bosman M., and Erasmus A.C. (2012). A critical review of the significance of food labeling during consumer decision making. *Journal of Consumer Sciences*, 40.
- Shirazi A., Lorestani H.Z., Mazidi A.K. (2013). "Investigating the effects of brand identity on customer loyalty from social identity perspective". *Iranian Journal of Management Studies*. 6 (2): 153–78.
- Temple N.J. (2020). Front-of-package food labels: A narrative review. *Appetite*. 2020 Jan 1; 144:104485.
- The Codex Alimentarius Commission. (2007). *Food Labeling: World Health Organization Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations*, 5th ed., pp. 1–9.
- Ushiyama S., Vingerhoeds M.H., Kanemura M., Kaneko D. and De Wijk R.A. (2021). Some insights into the development of food and brand familiarity: The case of soy sauce in the Netherlands. *Food Res. Int.*, 142.
- Verbeke W. and Ward R.W. (2006). Consumer interest in information cues denoting quality, traceability and origin: An application of ordered probit models to beef labels. *Food Quality and Preference* 17:453-467.
- Vojir F., Schübl E. and Elmadfa I. (2012). The origins of a global standard for food

Donald-Ase, Mary, Akhigbe, Evelyn Omolegho, Nwosu, Emmanuel C., Ifeanyi-Omeh, Chioma L., Gbenga-Philips, Peace C., Allison, Trust-Jah Tuae gwuchukwu and Kio-Mikietuoniso, Ogechi Attracta

Multidisciplinary Journal of Current Research and Review

Multi. J. Curr. Res. Rev.

Volume: 8; Issue: 06,

November-December, 2025

ISSN: 2763 –3642

Impact Factor: 6.41

Advance Scholars Publication

Published by International Institute of Advance Scholars Development

<https://aspjournals.net/Journals/index.php/mjerr/index>

quality and safety: Codex Alimentarius Austriacus and FAO/WHO Codex Alimentarius. *Int J Vitam Nutr Res.* 82(3):223-7.

Ye N., Morrin M. and Kampfer K. (2019). From Glossy to Greasy: The Impact of Learned Associations on Perceptions of Food Healthfulness. *J. Consum. Psychol.* 30, 96–124.

Donald-Ase, Mary, Akhigbe, Evelyn Omolegho, Nwosu, Emmanuel C., Ifeanyi-Omeh, Chioma L., Gbenga-Philips, Peace C., Allison, Trust-Jah Tuaegwuchukwu and Kio-Mikietuoniso, Ogechi Attracta